

at a uniform rate of 12.5 t/ha at 50 d of growth (N was 1.1% of fresh biomass). Excess was removed from the field. GM sown simultaneously in an adjacent field was cut, transported, and incorporated in the other treatment.

Short-duration (105 d) rice variety ADT36 was planted 1, 7, and 15 d after

GM incorporation. We planted at different days after submergence in the no-GM plot.

P and potash were basally applied to all plots; N was applied at varied rates and split as 50% basal, 25% active tillering, and 25% panicle initiation stages. Grain yield was recorded at 14% moisture; straw was sun-dried.

GM significantly increased rice grain and straw yields (see table). GM transported and incorporated gave the highest yield. Time interval after incorporation showed no significant variation in yield. This indicates the possibility of planting rice the day after GM incorporation. N at 100 kg/ha gave the highest yield. □

Crop management

Managing rice ratoons

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Beushaning is the practice of plowing young rice crops in 5–10 cm of standing water followed by laddering, redistributing seedlings to fill gaps, and hand weeding. Beushaning loosens and aerates the soil, enhances tillering and root growth, and improves drought and pest tolerance. We conducted field research to determine whether beushaning also improves ratoon rice yield.

CR1009 was grown during 1989 monsoon (Jul–Dec) and ratooned during 1989–90 summer (Dec–Apr). It was transplanted and fertilized with 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha. We harvested after 166 d and left 10- or 20-cm stubble. The ratoon was fertilized at 20-4.3-8.3, 40-8.7-16.7, or 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha. Half of the ratoon crop was beushaned.

Combinations of these treatments (2 × 3 × 2) were imposed on the ratoon crop laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Sarathi (119 d) was transplanted during summer for comparison.

Application of 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha to the ratoon crop significantly increased panicles/m², grains/panicle, and grain weight (Table 1).

Beushaning had no significant effect on any of the yield-contributing characters. Though it increased the tillering ability of the stubble, it decreased hills/m².

Ratoons from 10-cm-high stubble yielded 2 t/ha, 0.54 t more than the yield of ratoons from 20-cm-high stubble.

Table 1. Yield and yield characters of ratoon crops.^a

	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	Chaffy grains (no./panicle)	1,000- grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	
					Grain	Straw
Fertility level (kg/ha)						
N	4.3	8.3				
20	299	67	16.0	21.8	1.6	2.3
40	281	70	15.7	22.3	1.8	2.6
60	389	77	14.3	23.7	1.8	2.5
LSD (0.05)	49	2	ns	0.8	ns	ns
Stubble height (cm)						
10	333	74	14.0	22.4	2.0	2.9
20	313	69	16.6	22.8	1.5	2.1
LSD (0.05)	ns	2	2.5	ns	0.3	0.5
Cultural practice						
No beushaning	332	72	15.5	22.5	1.7	2.4
Beushaning	314	71	15.1	22.7	1.8	2.5
Mean	323	72	15.3	22.6	1.8	2.5

^ans = not significant.

Straw yield was also greater for the 10-cm stubble.

The ratoon crop yielded approximately half as much as the main crop. Ratoon crop duration was 47 d less than that of the main crop (Table 2).

The summer crop Sarathi yield was higher than that of the ratoon. Cultivation

cost was \$142/ha for the ratoon crop and \$209/ha for the summer crop. Net profit was \$15/ha more for the summer crop. Ratooning should not be practiced unless problems such as waterlogging or time constraints confront farmers. □

Table 2. Comparison of main and ratoon crops.

Character	Main crop Sarathi	Ratoon crop CR1009
Plant height (cm)	77.6	47.1
Hills (no./m ²)	49.6	44.9
Tillers (no./m ²)	270	451
Tillers (no./hill)	5.4	9.9
Panicles (no./m ²)	244	323
Panicles affected by stem borer (no./m ²)	20.6	14.2
Grains (no./panicle)	124	72
Chaffy grains (no./panicle)	22	15
Panicle length (cm)	22.2	16.7
1,000-grain weight (g)	24.3	22.6
Grain yield (t/ha)	3.2	1.8
Straw yield (t/ha)	4.9	2.5
Chaffy grain yield (t/ha)	0.3	0.1
Duration (d)	166	119
Grains (kg/ha per d)	19.5	14.7

Effect of plant growth enhancer on lowland rice yield

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We studied the effect of WOKOZIM, a growth enhancer extracted from seaweed, on lowland rice yield in 1989 wet season (WS) and 1990 dry season (DS) at irrigated sites in Maligaya and in Midsayap, North Cotabato.

Trials were laid out in randomized complete block design with four replications. Wetbed seedlings were transplanted 21 d after sowing. Treatments were the recommended fertilizer rate (60-30-30 kg NPK/ha in WS and 90-30-

Effect of WOKOZIM on lowland rice yields in Maligaya, Nueva Ecija, and Midsayap, Cotabato, 1989 WS and 1990 DS.

Treatment		Grainyield ^a (t/ha)	
NPK (kg/ha)	WOKOZIM (ml/ha)	Maligaya	Midsayap
1989 WS		<i>IR64</i>	<i>IR72</i>
60-30-30	0	2.8 b	3.6 b
60-30-30	450	3.4 ab	4.2 a
90-30-30	0	3.1 ab	3.4 b
90-30-30	450	3.7 a	4.1 a
1990 DS		<i>IR72</i>	<i>IR74</i>
90-30-30	0	4.6 b	2.8 a
90-30-30	450	5.0 ab	3.2 a
120-30-30	0	4.6 b	2.6 a
120-30-30	450	5.2 a	2.9 a

^aMean of four replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by LSD.

30 kg NPK/ha in DS); recommended fertilizer rate + WOKOZIM; farmers' fertilizer rate (90-30-30 kg NPK/ha in WS and 120-30-30 kg NPK/ha in DS); and farmers' fertilizer rate + WOKOZIM. We applied WOKOZIM to IR64 (WS) and IR72 (DS) at Maligaya and IR72 (WS) and IR74 (DS) in Midsayap.

WOKOZIM increased yield 16-21% during WS and 8-14% during DS (see table). We attributed this increase to more tillers, higher percentage of filled grains, and heavier grains. Other agronomic parameters showed no statistical differences among treatments. □

Effect of nitrogen levels and soil moisture conservation practices on rainfed rice

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We studied how six tillage methods and three N application levels affected grain and straw yields of rice during 1990 wet season. The soil was silty-clay loam with pH 5.8, 9.3 g organic C/ha, 502.8 kg available N/ha, 4.7 kg available P/ha, and 272.3 kg available K/ha in the top 15 cm.

The experiment was laid out in split-plot design with three replications. Tillage methods were in the main plots, N levels in the subplots (see table).

Effects of tillage practices and N levels on grain and straw yields of rainfed rice, 1990.

Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)		Treatment ^a	Yield (t/ha)	
	Grain	Straw		Grain	Straw
Tillage practices			N levels (kg/ha)		
Dry seeding (DSR)	1.2	3.0	40	1.3	2.8
DSR + halod (H)	1.6	3.4	80	1.5	3.5
DSR with deep tillage (DT)	1.5	3.7	120	1.6	3.8
DSRDT + H	1.7	3.5	LSD(0.05)	1.0	3.3
DSR + lantana mulch (LM)	1.4	3.4			
DSRDT + LM	1.5	3.3			
LSD(0.05)	1.5	ns			

^aHalod is plowing fields with standing water when rice is 15-20 cm.

Dry seeded rice (DSR) with deep tillage + halod (DSRDT + H) produced the most grain at 1.71 t/ha. Tillage

practice did not influence straw yield. Grain and straw yields increased significantly as N rates increased. □

Technical inefficiency of rice production in Chiang Mai, Thailand

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Rice is grown mainly during the wet season (Jun-Oct), followed by dry season (Nov-May) crops, in the lowland irrigated Chiang Mai Valley. Rice yields vary even with the same input levels, suggesting technical inefficiencies in production.

We randomly sampled and interviewed 193 rice farmers using a structured questionnaire. We collected 1989 data from four cropping systems: rice - soybean, rice - potato, rice - tomato, and rice - garlic.

We analyzed the data using the stochastic Cobb-Douglas frontier production model. Per farm rice grain output was the dependent variable. Independent variables were per farm inputs of cropping area, labor, fertilizer, pesticides, and herbicides.

Two error terms were specified: a random error with normal distribution (variation in yield due to random stresses beyond farmers' control, such as bad weather) and a one-sided error with half-normal distribution (loss due to farmer inefficiency).

Farmers averaged 7.5% rice yield loss, meaning the average sampled rice yield

was only 92.5% of potential yield (see table). Rice yield loss to technical inefficiency was more than 10% for 19 farmers. The most inefficient farmer lost 26.1%.

The T-test showed that inefficiency statistics were significant (p = 0.01). Further research, however, is needed to determine if increasing mean yield by 7.5% would be economical through the technical means considered in this analysis. □

Potential and observed rice grain yield in Chiang Mai, Thailand, 1989.^a

Actual yield (t/ha)	4.2
Potential yield (t/ha)	4.6
Yield loss due to technical inefficiency	
Percent	7.5
Amount (kg/ha)	342

^aBased on 193 observations.

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.